

Transnational Access project ARMSRACE

1. General information

Project acronym ARMSRACE

Project title Archaeological and Relief Modeling of the Sárvíz valley for Reconstruction of Ancient Climate Events

Type Scientific project

Scientific theme Connecting archeological settlement pattern with historic geomorphological and hidrological modelling based on remote sensing data in the Sarviz valley (Hungary).

Main scientific field and Specific discipline Humanities / Other-Humanities

Participants undertaking research

Name + link to id card	Research status	Email	Institution	Institution country	CV	Letter of reference	Publication
		Publication (3)					
		Publication (2)					
REMENYI Laszlo	Post-Graduate	laszlo.remenyi@kosz.gov.hu	Field Service for Cultural Heritage	Hungary			

Lead scientist's background

(scientific and aircraft measurements background and experience, English level) Expert in archaeological fieldwork, especially identifying sites on field, landscape elements, collecting contemporary written data, methodology of landscape and settlement archaeology

Recent relevant publications by application group in last 5 years (up to 5)

- [ARCHAEOLOGICAL REMOTE SENSING SURVEY: LIDAR, HYPERSPECTRAL AND AERIAL IMAGING IN ONE CAMPAIGN](#)
- [Project ARCHPLANE publication1](#)

Scientific problems being addressed by the experiments to be performed. Brief summary of the experiments Archaeological settlement network research and interpretation is only possible based on wide-scale measurements and reconstructions. In Transdanubia, environmental reconstructions were previously based on borehole datasets since no other surveys were carried out. Geoinformation systems and remote sensing allow for reconstruction experiments at a much larger scale. Several significant historic changes of climate is a known fact, but the impact of these on the settlements is yet unknown although essential for understanding the settlement network.

The central region of the Carpathian Basin is a floodplain which was especially affected by changes of climate. The topography and the already accumulated archaeological data of the study area is ideal for such a study. Our goal is to collect archaeological and topographic data from a pilot area and to build geomorphologic and hydrologic models based on these datasets, and to use these models to investigate the effect of climate changes on historic settlements through archaeological sites. Remote sensing data will be closely integrated with past and future fieldwork. LIDAR mapping provides input data for a Digital Terrain Model, which will be overlain in a GIS by the surveyed archaeological sites to delineate the borders of historic water bodies. Orthophotographs allow for the identification of cropmarks and other landscape elements indicating structures in the subsoil. The application of hyperspectral imaging to archaeology is relatively new, and we aim at testing the applicability of these images to archaeological fieldwork by investigating images of already known sites.

Aircraft DO228 - NERC - ARSF

Why this aircraft best suits the experiments? Proposed alternative aircraft The main parameter to be measured is the topographic elevation of the ground surface above sea level by airborne LIDAR. No other aircraft open for TA carries a topographic LIDAR, except for POLAR-5 AWI but the Laser altimeter needs a highly reflective surface which is not available here. NERC DO 228 is expected to be in the Balaton region because of the AIMWETLAB flights.

2. Description of the experiments

Scientific objectives / Proposed work / Anticipated output GIS-based investigation of settlement patterns with elevation models are very rare in Hungary, mostly taken place in the eastern part of the country (Great Plain). We have very limited knowledge on the project area. Hereinafter is a short history of research on the subject.

The GIS-based settlement-pattern research arrived to Hungary in the early 1990s through the microregional research initiated by English–Hungarian institutional and university cooperations. GIS-based survey and a spatial approach became an integral part of the surface excavations during the Gyomaendrőd and Upper Tisza Project (UTP) (Gyomaendrőd: Bökönyi (ed.) 1992, and Bökönyi (ed.) 1996; UTP: Chapman, Shiel, Passmore, Magyarai et al. (eds.) 2003). During the processing of these material several essays on the topic of spatial theory were written (e.g. Gillings 1995). Partially as a result of microregional research, environmental archaeology influenced Hungarian research more significantly (Visy 2002, Chapter II). The research approached from the methodology of environmental archaeology regarding the examination of several microregions brought interpretational possibilities ranging from the Paleolithic to the Middle Ages with some exciting results (Gál, Juhász, Sümegi (eds.) 2005; Zatykó, Juhász, Sümegi (eds.) 2007). Nevertheless, the research laid emphasis on environmental archaeology.

The results of the methodological school of the English-speaking world proved fertile for the settlement archaeology of both the Middle Ages and the Neolithic, roughly at the same time. Medieval settlement archaeology studies are mostly coordinated by the Department of Medieval Studies (see the volume of essays by Laszlovszky and Szabó (eds.) 2003). The methodological problems of sources were studied by Péter Szabó (Szabó 2003, 2005) and József Laszlovszky (Laszlovszky 2003). The reconstruction of a settlement of the Árpadian Age in the regions between the Danube and Tisza rivers conducted by Marianna Bálint (Bálint 1998), and the settlement reconstructual studies by Csilla Zatykó from a spatial archaeological stance (Zatykó 2003) provide further significant aids of methodology.

In Neolithic studies, Andrew Sherratt was the first to deal with questions of the settlement network in connection with the topographical research of Békés County (Sherratt 1983), but one have to mention the Ecsegfalva project also (Whittle 2007). Regarding the Copper Age of the Körös regions, the works of Parkinson (2006) and Parkinson-Gyucha (2008), and in the Benta Valley the studies of Poroszlai–Vicze (2000, 2005) have to be mentioned.

Unlike many of the former projects, ARMSRACE is not based on an already excavated archaeological site only to search its surroundings. We would examine the whole settlement pattern of the valley as limited as we may by field walking, however these limits can be extended with remote sensing.

The course of the water is regulated from the end of the 19. century and the former marshland had been drained. We have already reconstructed the boundaries of these marshland before the drainage with the help of surveys made preceding the drainage works (Stibranyi 2008). But we do not know much about these boundaries before that time. By field surveys we can collect every surface data of archeological sites in the valley, but its important to have a digital elevation model of the terrain, so we will be able to interpolate it to the whole walley and verify it. E. g. if we find the place of each roman settlement according to the same water level, (which is of course not equal with the same height, since Sárvíz is a river) then it can be taken as a prove. Moreover we can compare this with other ages.

Due to the drainage the water means no obstacle today, so with LIDAR technology we can collect surface data to generate the digital elevation model. In this low lying region even the slightest change in the water level means a difference in settlement pattern. Assuming that these settlements had tried to settle near the water, we can reconstruct some aspects of the water level change during history, therefore we can examine the connection between settlement pattern and climate changes.

Beside the elevation model, the abundance of archaeological sites means another opportunity to study them with other methods, which can take place in the same flight, similar to the AIMWETLAB project, like orthophotographic images, hyperspectral aerial images addition to the LIDAR, by which we shall not only be able to make a digital elevation model, but to search for signs that could help us localizing and interpreting archeological sites. Moreover with these images we may be able to examine not only sites, but other relict landscape elements also (e. g. holloways, roads, barriers).

After analysing images and surface data we would set up a team on students and experts and publish its interpretation in the institute yearbook, not to mention the conferencies both in Hungary and abroad. Interdisciplinary works are also possible with hungarian geology, geophysics experts.

Weather conditions (e.g. clouds, atmospheric stability, wind speed and direction, weather...) The LIDAR measurements are possible under weather conditions that are usually not optimal for remote sensing. Some haze, cloud cover or even fog is acceptable and would not affect achieving the main scientific goals of the project. Nevertheless, hyperspectral imaging requires completely cloud-free skies or evenly distributed thin, high clouds, and aerial photogrammetric imaging is also optimal under good lighting conditions and atmospheric cover.

Time constraints (time of the day, pass(es) of satellites, weekends, season...) The lidar measurements do not need to be linked to any time of the year or the day.

Orthographic photos are more dependent on the vegetation. In the region, most of the area is ploughed, main plants are grain and corn, former good, the latter worse for photos. Winter conditions also have some advantages as the soil and soil patterns are visible then. The scientific aim of the project can be met by measuring in time of the year.

Location(s) and reason for that choice Map of general area: [Project ARMSRACE: Detailed map](#)

The Study area is the valley of the Sárvíz River in County Fejér in Central Hungary.

This is an altogether 100 km long river which connects the Sárrét wetland with the Danube river. Its western bank is the loess ridge of Káloz-Igar, moderately hilly, but its eastern part is a flat region, the westernmost part of the Great Hungarian Plain called the Mezőföld. In this project we are focusing only on its northern part of the Mezőföld region, which has an approximate length of 60 km. On the flat eastern part even small changes of water level cause large shifts in the shores of the wetlands, and the settlements, which use the nearest suitable areas to the water level follow this changes. This was necessary because the loess bedrock of the region is highly permeable to water and wells could not reach the low-lying water table.

This area was also a very important communication channel both for N-S and E-W travel and thus was quite densely populated in the past 8000 years including the Roman Age town of Gorsium which was one of the largest settlements of the time and is included in the study area. The network of villages was the most dense in the northern part of the region since the road to the Italian Peninsula and the Adriatic used since the Prehistory in this area. The dense settlement structure, the low topography and the constraint that only surface waters were available can be an excellent indicator for reconstructing hydrology and climate.

The area was drained in the 19th century, so all areas that were submerged up to the Early Modern Age can be studied in the field. The southern end of the area – which is less frequented archaeologically – is one of the three pilot area of the proposed Hungarian Landscape Value Cataster, the archaeological survey of which is going to be performed by our institute.

Number of flights / flight hours and flight patterns The NERC DO228 requires about 5-6 hours of flight time from the home base to the study area, and another 5-6 hours on the way back. Clustering with AIMWETLAB or other flights in the region would divide this time between several projects. The measurement flight requires 4 hours from take-off to landing (both at Sármellék airport). The planned width for the

measured swath is 1000 m, the study area is about 60*10 km, the pattern to be flown is a simple parallel pattern with a path interval of 800 m to ensure 20% overlap between measured swaths.

Other constraints or requirements

3. Key measurements required to achieve science aims

Parameter / measurement required The key parameter to be measured is the elevation of the ground surface above sea level by LIDAR. The orthophotographs are of secondary importance but would aid interpretation of the topography, and hyperspectral measurements would be needed in order to extend knowledge of the applicability of this method to archaeological site identification in the future.

If applicable, specify TA instrument required None

Instruments to be provided by hosting aircraft operator (*basic instrumentation owned by the aircraft operator described on EUFAR website only*) AISA Eagle/Hawk hyperspectral imaging system
Leica RCD 105 digital imaging camera
Leica ALS 50-II LIDAR

Instruments to be provided by scientific group (*Have already been flown. On which aircraft? Do the instruments have their own data acquisition system?*) Our department is executing archaeological fieldwork with ground teams throughout the year. Therefore we have infrastructure for archaeological fieldwork (all terrain vehicle, staff, GPS, GIS-expert, GIS software maps, know-how etc.), Our institute is eligible for archaeological works.

Instrument operators onboard (in addition to those provided by the aircraft operator). If so, how many? 0

If applicable, plans for simultaneous field work plans / ground equipment to be used Field archaeological surveys do not need to be carried out simultaneously with the flight. In the study area, field teams will identify archaeological sites based on the LIDAR data, the images, and field signals (pottery shards, surface marks etc.) during foot surveys of the whole mapped area.

4. Data processing and analysis

Methodology for handling the data and analysis of output (*airborne data acquisition, ground-truthing / observations, data processing and interpretation*) The main goal with the data is to find anomalies in the landscape to reconstruct human presence throughout the centuries. All three methods (LIDAR, hyperspectral and aerial images) can show different kinds of anomalies, which – accompanied by fieldwork – can produce results on a very wide spatial and time scale which is unparalleled in other Hungarian Archaeology studies.

With LIDAR data we can create the actual DEM of the Sárvíz valley, which is essential for the water level reconstruction and relief modeling. By examining a hillshade image of the DEM (raster or TIN model) even the slightest slope anomalies become visible. Combining this with slope and aspect images together with vector data (rivers, roads etc.) we can find preferred sites for historic settlements. The terrain from the LIDAR will be the base for modeling the waterline.

Hyperspectral images are excellent for examination of soil types and vegetation. With a relatively good resolution the anomalies are also visible, which can show added information (extra iron content, buried buildings, disturbed soils etc). With the accurate vegetation map we can conclude to the potential vegetation of the Sárvíz valley. The advantages of hyperspectral images are not well known and used in landscape-scale archaeology, and this project will contribute to providing further knowledge on this topic. The hyperspectral images have to be cleaned from the noises (for example removing atmospheric noise by using software provided free of charge by NERC), after that we can select the right images from the data cube for further analysis and can make classifications. The classifications will be based on reference areas on the ground (vegetation and soil samples).

Because of the excellent resolution, aerial images are best for fieldwork. It is essential to orthorectify the images. Because of the high resolution they are also good for finding anomalies which are cannot be seen on the LIDAR or the hyperspectral images (for example certain visible colouring on the fields, cropmarks etc).

Resources available to support the project beyond the flying/data acquisition period (*funding, cooperation with other projects, manpower for analysis of results and preparation of user report, availability of laboratory facilities...*) Salaries and field expenses of the ground truthing and GIS analysis teams will be provided by institute funds, also covering the costs of archiving and identifying artefacts found.

5. Planning

Starting date: 16-08-2010

Ending date: 29-08-2010

Preferred and acceptable dates (*season / time windows*) The lidar measurements do not need to be linked to any time of the year or the day. Orthographic photos are more dependent on the vegetation. In the region, most of the area is ploughed, main plants are grain and corn, former good, the latter worse for photos. Winter conditions also have some advantages as the soil and soil patterns are visible then. The scientific aim of the project can be met by measuring in time of the year.

Agreement to share aircraft time (*project clustering, cost sharing*) Yes

6. Other useful comments

Training benefit of the project (*e.g. spread potential of airborne research to a wide scientific community; training of research students in experimental planning, methodology, data analysis and applications, etc*) I shall teach landscape archaeology and examining archaeological

settlement patterns due in 2010 in the Archaeological Institute of Eötvös Loránd University in Budapest. In the following semester (2010 autumn or 2011 spring) I'm planning to demonstrate this, and moreover to build a team from the participant students for further data analysing.

If possible, 3 scientific reviewers that EUFAR may contact Prof. Dr. Laszlovszky József, Central European University, Department for Medieval Studies
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Prof. Dr. Feld István, senior lecturer, Eötvös Loránd Science University, Institute for Archaeology, Head of Department for Medieval and Early Modern Age Archaeology.
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Dr. Mark Gillings, Senior Lecturer in Landscape Archaeology, Director of Undergraduate Studies, University of Leicester, School of Archaeology and Ancient History.
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Sources of funding of the project and of related projects (if clustering with existing projects supported either by national or other EC funding, how the project add additional or complementary aims to the already funded experiments) Archaeological fieldwork and image analysis are funded by the Field Service for Cultural Heritage in Hungary. The salaries of the researchers and the field and computer equipment required are provided by the employing institute.

Scientific training provided by lead scientist to other EUFAR sponsored scientists within the fields of the proposed experiments and analysis Yes

Number of students 8

Number of days recommended 5

Knowledge about EUFAR opportunities from Advertisement at conferences/scientific events

Related documents

You may need to login to the EUFAR Back Office to see all the documents.

- [Project ARMSRACE: Bounding box](#)
- [Project ARMSRACE: Figure for FOI](#)
- [Project ARMSRACE: overview map](#)
- [Project ARMSRACE: T&S estimate](#)

7. Reporting

Campaign dates: From 19-08-2010 to 19-08-2010

Participants

Name	First time flying this aircraft	Participation in the campaign	Number of visits to campaign	Duration of stay	T&S reimbursed	Additional information
STIBRANYI Mate	Yes	On site	1	1	Yes	
PADANYI-GULYAS Gergely	Yes	On site	1	1	No	
REMENYI Laszlo	Yes	Remotely	0	0	No	

Meetings

Start date	End date	Location	Title	Number of persons from the group attending the meeting	Overall number of attendees
19-08-2010	19-08-2010	Sármellék	visiting the aircraft, dinner	2	4

Confirmation of the user access (list of flights, number of flight hours) / Evaluation of the service provided by the operator: mark (1-Unsatisfactory, 2-Insufficient, 3-Satisfactory, 4-Good, 5-Excellent) and comments

Flight date: 19/08/10 Number of flights: 1 Flight hours: 4 Flight height: 8950 ft Number of lines: 9+1 Evaluation of the service: 5 Comments: The operators were helpful, informal and fully up to the task, we could work together effectively. Our project was connected with several other projects in Hungary (AIMWETLAB, ADDRESS, Stirling University project: Bio-optical properties and hyperspectral remote sensing of Lake and Kis Balaton). We had agreed previously that ARMSRACE's priority is behind AIMWETLAB and the Stirling University project. Due to weather conditions our flight window had to be reduced, therefore the flight height and the swath width was increased (e.g. swath width changed from the planned 1000 m to 2000 m). However, we have been informed that on time and agreed on the decision.

Quality of data and associated service

Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML) was kind to allow András Zlinszky (lead scientist of project AIMWETLAB) and Gergely Padányi-Gulyás (GIS engineer of project ARMSRACE) to visit PML for giving an insight about the data processing in January 2011. The pre-processed data arrived in Hungary in February 2011. We are also thankful to PML for the online help at the first stages of the data processing. Since the LIDAR was more important for us, due to limited resources we only processed and work with these data. The quality of the data is below the

formerly expected, due to the increased swath width caused by bad weather conditions. The point density is around 0.5 hits/sqm (see above).

Main achievements / Further plans for analysis

Up to now the main achievement was the removal of buildings and forests of the LIDAR point cloud using a self-developed method in the open source GRASS GIS software. Further plan is to acquire a proper DEM, removing the dense vegetation (mainly crops). For this we have to isolate the vegetated areas, which will be achieved with two different methods: using LIDAR intensity values and hyperspectral images. For hyperspectral data processing we participate in a spin-off project, called ANAGHLIA (ANalysis And Ground truthing of Hyperspectral and Lidar Images in Archaeology) with the KU Leuven (Catholic University of Leuven), VITO (Flemish Institute for Technological Research) and GHIA (Groningen Institute of Archaeology).

Difficulties encountered

Due to low point density (0.5 hits/sqm) and full leaf-on conditions the DEM extraction proved to be a very difficult task. In dense forests and ploughed areas (corn, wheat, sunflower etc.) there is hardly any difference between the first and the last returns, and in most cases there are no ground hits at all. With a self-developed method we managed to filter out forests and buildings, but the extremely dense vegetation removal is still in progress (see above).

Publications linked to the project

- [ARCHAEOLOGICAL REMOTE SENSING SURVEY: LIDAR, HYPERSPECTRAL AND AERIAL IMAGING IN ONE CAMPAIGN](#)
- [Project ARCHPLANE publication1](#)

Website of the project